

Academic Job Interview Prep—Recommendations

This is a list of lessons and tips drawn from my experience of five short-list campus visits to US and European institutions in 2017, 2018, and 2022. I visited:

- an R2 in the western US
- a public, teaching-focused college in the southern US
- an R1 in the northeastern US
- an R1 in the southern US
- a research-focused university in Ireland (where I am currently employed)

As a result, my experiences cover a relatively wide range of institutions, from smaller-scale and teaching-focused to larger-scale research universities in both the US and Europe.

Before You Go

First things first: I've found job interviews to be surprisingly fun. The most stressful part of the actual interview is the anticipation and preparation—as a result, my academic work slows to a crawl in the days preceding the campus visit. However, I've never had a bad experience¹ with faculty, students, or the audience attending my talks, and I have always enjoyed meeting new people and explaining my research. Your mileage may vary, however—there are plenty of horror stories out there. My point is that as an early-stage ECR I assumed my first campus interviews would be combative, performative, trials-by-fire, full of senior faculty explicitly questioning my expertise and attempting to rattle me. In my experience in anthropology or archaeology departments, at least, that has not been the case.

Remember that they are trying to sell themselves to you as much as you are trying to sell yourself to them, and if people are jerks, it's probably an honest signal of larger problems at that institution. Even if the experience is unpleasant on that day or in that meeting, it's a reflection of them, not of you. If you have this kind of negative experience, at least you've learned something valuable: this is probably not an institution you want to be at anyways. I write this with the obvious caveat that sometimes you only have one interview and so you only have one option. My perspective has entailed taking a long-game approach to campus interviews. To relieve *some* of the psychological pressure, I try to treat every visit as an opportunity to network or practice interview skills. In at least one instance, a campus visit (for a job I didn't get, which was crushing at the time) led to a postdoc at the same institution down the line.

Be yourself, unless you are introvert, in which case, be a slightly more extroverted version of yourself. The strain of trying to be someone you are not will become apparent almost immediately, and it's not worth it in the wrong run.

I have been surprised by the degree to which non-academic chat is welcomed, but a big part of the interview involves demonstrating that you're a friendly colleague that people would want to work with. Don't allow meetings to be entirely overrun by your shared interest in Neil Gaiman novels, but a digression for a few minutes emphasizes that you bring more to the table than just your academic CV. Even if you don't get the job, you may make a valuable connection that leads you to collaborating with these people again in the future, or just have a new conference buddy.

¹ Though ask me in the future about missing PowerPoint photos, unanticipated early breakfast pick-ups, emergency tailoring, cancelled appointments, exploding soda bottles, and locked parking garages.

It is perfectly acceptable to contact the search committee chair, or whoever the point person is for the search, to ask for your visit itinerary in advance. Even a preliminary schedule can be helpful. If you email to ask about your itinerary more than a week before your visit, it's unlikely they'll have it ready, however.

Once I get my schedule, I create a cheat sheet to remember who faculty are, including the photograph from their website (Side note: People often have extremely unrepresentative photos posted on department websites). I've started using this table format to organize my notes and remember who's who:

[PHOTO]	NAME POSITION FIELD
Educational History	
Previous Positions	
Tenure timeline	
Research and Teaching Interests	
Specific Positions	
Current Projects	
Personal Network Overlap	
Comments/Thoughts	

Prepare some questions in advance. I've begun creating a separate word document where I write out specific questions for specific faculty members, and then consult it during the interview. I recommend going through the CVs of everyone you will meet—not to memorize that they were the graduate student representative on the finance committee in 1983, but to look at what they've done since arriving at their current institution. Do they teach the same core course you'll be asked to teach? Have they accumulated a big chunk of internal research support? Are they collaborating with the teaching center to write a SoTL paper? Asking questions like "I noticed that you received a Summer Teaching Fellowship in 2015 to work on a project on lithic procurement with an undergraduate student—can you tell me more about institutional support for undergraduate research?" - will show that you've done your homework. I don't try to memorize these questions anymore because you simply meet too many people during the interview process. Consulting a list and having specific questions for *them* at the very least shows that you are prepared.

The Job Talk

Practice it a million times.² When I asked for advice from the woman who gave one of the most polished archaeology job talks I saw at the University of Michigan, she told me that she made sure

² Five to seven.

that she knew her talk cold. I took this advice to heart, and since then I am heartily sick of my job talk, but people have told me that I sound very prepared.

Not every run through needs to cover the entire presentation (though do that at least one or two times to make sure you're hitting the mark, time wise). If you are struggling with your methods section, then practice JUST the methods section several times. This requires a significant amount of discipline as you will want to avoid the parts of the talk that are the weakest as these make you most uncomfortable. It is, however, a necessary part of the process, and the more you practice in advance the smoother it will go on the day.

Know what you want to say on each slide. I have now written out most of my slides, and when I'm putting things together or adding new slides, I try to make the photographs and figures reference what I want to say. Obviously, limit your text on the slides themselves.

If you can afford it (and if you're teaching this is a good idea anyways, because Murphy's Law necessitates that you will not be able to locate these items before the one class in which you actually need them), have your own dongle and slide changer. Practice the talk using the slide changer and it'll be an extra cue that you know what you're doing in front of an audience.

Tell a story, and don't be afraid to be redundant about it. Have a **big opening question** and come back to that at the end of the talk. If your talk is divided into discrete sections, concisely summarize what each section has discussed. Everything will seem evident to you, but the audience is going to be sitting through several of these talks and it is easy to get lost. Giving them a road map will win you points and make your research more comprehensible.

When creating clean graphics, the Remove Background tool in PowerPoint is, as the youths would say, *100*.

A Note on European Job Talks

The one European job talk that I've given had a markedly different format than the US job talks I'm used to, which are sprawling, 45-50 minute affairs that meander from research question to research question.

In Ireland, in contrast, I was asked to give two fifteen-minute talks. The minimal prompts were explicit about the perils of going over time, so the pacing had to be tight. As a result, I actually printed out my talk scripts and partially read them. Fifteen minutes is a vanishingly small amount of time, and rather than obsess about hitting the mark exactly, I decided to make sure I didn't go over. It's possible to give an engaged and active talk from notes—maintain eye contact with the audience, don't drop into robotic monotone, and incorporate some (short) ad libbing based on the signals you're getting from people watching—it just requires practice.

If you are going to read a talk, I strongly recommend printing out notes as well as having your notes written out in PowerPoint presenter view. Murphy's Law necessitates that something will go wrong the day you are presenting—maybe you have to give the talk on a Mac when you are a PC person, or maybe presenter view refuses to work on the school computer. Try to have a back-up plan, just in case, and don't get too flustered if things don't go exactly according to plan.

The Undergrad Class / Graduate Seminar

Before beginning to plan your lecture or seminar, figure out what the format will be.

Important things to know, that you can ask the search committee chair/point person, include:

- How is the room organized (e.g. amphitheater, seminar-sized table, individual desks/tables)?
- How many students will be attending?
- Are there assigned readings for this class?
- Can I assign readings for this class?
- Will the talk be part of an existing course, or is this an additional meeting that students are required to attend?
- Will faculty be attending?
- Do students have any background in [insert topic here—anthropology, bioarchaeology, etc.]?

If it's a class that you have not taught before, say, hypothetically "Race as a Social Construct" (no joke, I had to teach this to a group of undergrads I'd never met, in the southern US...) use your grad school and professional networks to access templates, readings, and get advice about the topic. I talked to several other biological anthropologists about the best recent literature on this topic, and it helped me feel more prepared.

If it's a graduate student seminar, see if you have any graduates of that program in your network who can give you some insight into seminar culture, or simply ask the search committee chair. My understanding of grad seminars is that the students are supposed to act as junior colleagues and active participants, but have some back-up plans in place in case students are less motivated to participate than you anticipated.

General Preparations

Buy a package of cough drops and bring some herbal tea for the evenings. You will be talking to people for the entire day and will also have to speak for forty-five minutes or so while giving your job talk. It's good to be pre-emptive about possible sore/scratchy throats. Having Tums on hand can be helpful too as you will be travelling and possibly eating unfamiliar food. Credit to [Caroline VanSickle](#) for this tip.

Know your limits. When I interview, I go to bed early (c. 10:00 PM) and get up at 5:30/6:00 if I feel the need to review or practice my talk. I am more focused in the mornings, and I know trying to do additional prep after a day of interviews is doomed to failure, so when I get back to the hotel, I cordon off the part of my brain dedicated to dealing with the interview, read an engrossing book/talk to my partner, and hit the hay.

As a follow-up, if you are a coffee/tea drinker, figure out how to access coffee at 5:30/6:00 AM. I have occasionally made coffee the night before and just drunk it cold when breakfast rooms don't open until 7. I'm gross, I know.

This is a new one, learned the hard way in 2018. Check that your interview clothes actually fit, before you wash or dry-clean them, and definitely check that they fit before you pack them!

Save all your food and transportation receipts. Most universities will cover the food you have to purchase because you're travelling, as well as additional forms of transport such as taxis or buses.

Figure out where the iron is as soon as you get to the hotel. My second job interview the room did not have an iron, and it took me about half an hour to call someone for instructions, locate the iron, and access the iron. These are not things you want to be doing the morning before you give a job talk.

If you can avoid working on the plane/journey, avoid it. My first few interviews I just read Terry Pratchett novels, and as a result I think I arrived better rested.

Be prepared to roll with the punches (see Footnote 1). Things will go awry, and unpredictable incidents will occur. Though it is tempting to try to prepare for everything, it is not actually possible—at a certain point, you have to trust your ability to think on your feet. Faculty will be playing close attention to how you react to disruptions and calamity, so keep an even keel and realize that instead of ruining your interview, unanticipated problems are an opportunity to show off what a good colleague and collaborator you would be.

I have heard arguments both for and against sending thank you notes. I personally lack the mental energy to obsess over the intricacies of etiquette associated with a handwritten thank you note after getting back from a visit. My strategy so far has been to email the search committee chair a thank you, and then shoot emails to anyone I met who I felt I really connected with—typically I follow up with copies of papers we discussed, or links to a website we talked about, etc.

As soon as you get back from the visit, organize and scan your receipts. I recommend the free app [Scannable](#), which allows you to scan documents with your phone camera. Then, create an itemized list of what you need to be reimbursed for, and contact the department administrator to ask what processes to follow to be reimbursed. If you put this step off, chances are receipts will go missing or you will simply never get around to doing it, and most trips I spend \$100–\$300 on travel and food.

GOOD LUCK!